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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“TWO LOVELY SONG”

I looked up high,
and the galaxy made me smile

Dash—
A shooting star flashed

I wished the stars to sing for me
I hope for them to ring in the vast
But maybe all they're meant to do is shine—
no voice, just light that lasts.

The milky way now starts to glow
It shows me the way and there I saw
The woman I love, standing in grace—
With two small stars held in embrace.

One is five, the other's three,
And both light up the world for me.

The stars did not sing after all—
They taught my heart to play a song

Uno and Dos— my lovely song
Their tiny hands are a place where I belong

Now—
my heart beats in stereo
For they turn my chaos into calm
Their laughter now— my lifetime psalm

